

was required for complete reduction. 1 ml of sodium nitrite for diazotisation and 2 ml of α -naphthol solutions were sufficient for coupling.

Beer's law was obeyed in the range 0.4–3.3 ppm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $6.98 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0042 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively for parathion. The reproducibility of the method was checked by analysing 25 $\mu\text{g}/25 \text{ ml}$ of parathion for a period of 8 days. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ± 0.0045 and $\pm 1.87\%$ respectively.

The following foreign species (in ppm) do not interfere in the estimation of 1 ppm parathion: Ca^{++} , Pb^{++} and Sr^{++} (upto 500), Cd^{++} , Mn^{++} and phosphate (upto 500), formaldehyde, Mg^{++} , Ni^{++} and Fe^{++} (upto 250), sulphate, aniline, phenol and Cu^{++} (upto 150), DDT, aldrin, endrin and malathion (upto 500).

Application: The method was applied in the determination of parathion in samples of vegetables foliage and soil.

The parathion was extracted from various crushed samples of vegetables and foliages in n-hexane as reported⁴, and analysed by the proposed and compared with the Buckley⁴ method (Table 1).

Known amounts of finely ground soil samples were washed with ethanol ($2 \times 20 \text{ ml}$) and made upto the volume with demineralised water. An aliquot of this solution was then analysed by the proposed as well as by the Buckley⁴ method (Table 1).

The recoveries from the samples are better even without the removal of coloured pigments and in low levels, in comparison to other methods. Parathion and methyl parathion can be precisely determined down to 0.4 ppm using the proposed method.

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A New Spectrophotometric Method for Determination of Acrylonitrile in Traces and its Application to Biological Samples

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ACRYLONITRILE¹ is used in various industries and organic synthesis and is toxic. Various methods have been reported for its determination^{2,3}.

A new spectrophotometric method is reported here for the trace determination of acrylonitrile. Acrylonitrile is converted into cyanide on reacting with alkaline potassium permanganate⁴ and the cyanide so formed on reaction with saturated bromine water is converted into cyanogen bromide which reacts with pyridine to form glutaconic aldehyde and then coupled with aqueous phloroglucinol to give red-violet polymethine dye in alkaline medium which obeys Beer's law in the range of 10–70 μg per 10 ml of the final solution (1–7 ppm). The method has been successfully applied for the determination of acrylonitrile in air, blood and urine.

Experimental

A Carl Zeiss spekol and calibrated glassware were used. Analytical grade reagents and distilled water were used.

A solution (1 mg ml^{-1}) of acrylonitrile in 5% ethanol was prepared and a working standard of 20 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ solution was used. Alkaline potassium permanganate solution was prepared by mixing 0.1 N KMnO_4 (35 ml) with 0.1 N NaOH (15 ml). A 1.5% (w/v) aqueous solution of sodium arsenite and 2 M HCl were used.

Pyridine reagent was prepared by mixing freshly distilled pyridine (18 ml) with concentrated HCl (3 ml) and diluted with distilled water (12 ml). A saturated aqueous solution of phloroglucinol and bromine was used.

Procedure: To an aliquot containing 10 to 70 μg (1–7 ppm) of acrylonitrile, alkaline potassium permanganate solution (1 ml) was added and kept for 2 min. The excess of potassium permanganate was then decolourised by a few drops of sodium arsenite followed by 2 M HCl (0.2 ml). Then bromine solution (0.5 ml) was added and the excess bromine destroyed by the dropwise addition of sodium arsenite. To it pyridine reagent (0.3 ml) followed by phloroglucinol (1 ml) were added. After 1 min the volume was made upto the mark with sodium hydroxide to make pH of the final solution ~ 9 and then measured the absorbance

at 540 nm against distilled water as reference. The reagent blank was prepared in the same manner which gave no colour under these conditions.

Results and Discussion

The red-violet coloured dye shows a maximum absorbance at 540 nm.

Effect of varying reagent concentration: A minimum of 1 ml of alkaline potassium permanganate was required for complete oxidation of acrylonitrile into cyanide. A 0.5 ml of bromine water was sufficient for complete bromination. The excess bromine and potassium permanganate caused no change in the absorbance as the excess were destroyed by sodium arsenite. A minimum of 0.2 ml of pyridine was needed for the reaction. Constant absorbance values were obtained with 1–5 ml of phloroglucinol.

It was found that 3–5 min were required for full colour development and the dye was stable at pH ~ 9–9.6 for 10 min in the temperature range 20–40°.

The system obeyed Beer's law in the range 10–70 µg of acrylonitrile in 10 ml of the final solution. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $5.3 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 0.01 µg cm^{-2} respectively. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be 0.007 and 2.33% respectively, for 20 µg of acrylonitrile in 10 ml of final solution.

The tolerance limit (in ppm) for various species associated with acrylonitrile (2 ppm) is as follows: acetonitrile (100), acetone, formaldehyde (1000), phenol, aniline (80), ethanol (1200), benzene (3000); Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} (250), Pb^{2+} , Sn^{2+} (500), Al^{3+} (200), Zn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Fe^{2+} (100). Cyanides and thiocyanates showed positive interference. Metal ions forming hydroxide in alkaline medium were masked with EDTA and others with Rochelle salt.

Application: The proposed method has been successfully applied for the determination of acrylonitrile in air, urine and blood. Due to non-availability of the standard air samples synthetic air samples were obtained by evaporating acrylonitrile into the fuming cup-board. Then the vapours were drawn into the absorbing solution (alkaline potassium permanganate) taken in two impingers connected to an air sampling train⁵, kept outside the fuming cup-board. Then it was analysed by the proposed method and aniline–pyridine method⁴. The results obtained were found to be in agreement.

Synthetic samples were prepared by adding known amounts of acrylonitrile to each sample of

TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF THE SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD WITH THAT REPORTED

Sl. no.	Reagent ^a	Range of determination ppm
1.	Aniline–pyridine ^a	10–40
2.	Pyridine ^b	5–30
3.	Laurylmercaptan ^c	5–50
4.	Phloroglucinol ^d	1–7

^aRef. 4, ^bRef. 3, ^cRef. 7, ^dPresent work.

blood and urine prior to analyses after deproteination with trichloroacetic acid as recommended⁶. The recovery range was 92–96%.

The method has been compared with other spectrophotometric methods reported for its determination and found to be more sensitive (Table 1).

The proposed method is rapid, sensitive and free from co-pollutants. The method has been successfully applied for the analysis of acrylonitrile in air and biological samples.

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